

D11.2 EOOSC Integration Suite with the initial set of adapters

30/09/2025

Abstract

This deliverable provides the status of the initial set of software adapters that enable interoperability across EOOSC services. It details their design, development status, and designated plan, supporting seamless integration within the EOOSC ecosystem.

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Table of contents

Document Description	1
Revision History	3
Table of contents	4
Tables	5
1. Introduction	7
1.1. Scope and Purpose of the document	7
1.2. Structure of the document.....	7
2. Status of the Initial Set of Adapters	8
2.1. EOSC Core service adapters.....	8
2.1.1. Accounting for Services Adapter.....	8
2.1.2. Helpdesk Adapter	9
2.1.3. IF Registry Adapters	10
2.1.3.1. Interoperability Framework Guidelines Discovery Adapter	10
2.1.3.2. Interoperability Framework Guidelines Management Adapter	11
2.1.4. Messaging Adapter.....	11
2.1.5. Monitoring Adapter.....	12
2.1.6. PID Adapter	13
2.1.7. Research Product Accounting Adapters.....	14
2.1.7.1. COUNTER Adapter for DSpace platform	14
2.1.7.2. COUNTER Adapter for ePrints platform.....	15
2.1.7.3. Generic Usage Activity Tracker for OpenAIRE.....	15
2.1.8. Research Product Catalogue Adapter (OAI-PMH end-point for SQL Postgres Database).....	16
2.1.9. Service Catalogue Adapters.....	17
2.1.9.1. Service Discovery Adapter	17
2.1.9.2. Provider and Service Management Adapter.....	17
2.1.9.3. Administration and Audit Adapter.....	18
2.1.9.4. Insights and Statistics Adapter	19
2.2. EOSC Horizontal service adapters	19
2.2.1. EOSC Data Transfer Client	19
2.2.2. JupyterLab libraries for service provisioning and data staging	20
2.2.3. Metadata gathering of TOSCA templates	21
2.2.4. Data access across hosting environments.....	21
2.2.5. Python libraries for the EOSC exchange Jupyter service management	22
2.3. EOSC Community service adapters	23
2.3.1. Implementation Plan for the EOSC Community Adapters	23
2.3.2. Exchange Services as Foundations for Adapter Development.....	23
3. Conclusion	26
Acronyms.....	27

Tables

Table 1 - Accounting for Services Adapter	9
Table 2 - Helpdesk Adapter	10
Table 3 - Interoperability Framework Guidelines Discovery Adapter	11
Table 4 - Interoperability Framework Guidelines Management Adapter	11
Table 5 - Messaging Adapter	12
Table 6 - Monitoring Adapter	13
Table 7 - PID Adapter	14
Table 8 - COUNTER Adapter for DSpace platform	15
Table 9 - COUNTER Adapter for ePrints platform	15
Table 10 - Generic Usage Activity Tracker for OpenAIRE	16
Table 11 - Research Product Catalogue Adapter (OAI-PMH end-point for SQL Postgres Database)	16
Table 12 - Service Discovery Adapter	17
Table 13 - Provider and Service Management Adapter	18
Table 14 - Administration and Audit Adapter	19
Table 15 - Insights and Statistics Adapter	19
Table 16 - EOSC Data Transfer Client	20
Table 17 - JupyterLab libraries for service provisioning and data staging	21
Table 18 - Metadata gathering of TOSCA templates	22
Table 19 - Data access across hosting environments	22
Table 20 - Python libraries for the EOSC exchange Jupyter service management	23
Table 21 - Identified Exchange Services and their classification	25

Executive Summary

This deliverable focuses on the initial set of adapters designed to enable interoperability among various services, tools, and data sources across the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem. These adapters act as middleware components that bridge technical differences between systems, supporting standardised protocols and APIs in alignment with the EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF) Guidelines¹.

We categorise the adapters into three key groups:

1. EOSC Core Service Adapters: These support integration with fundamental EOSC services.
2. EOSC Horizontal Service Adapters: These provide cross-domain functionalities.
3. EOSC Community Service Adapters: These are being developed in collaboration with Pilot Nodes to serve the specific needs of research communities. A plan is in place for recognising, documenting, and onboarding community-specific adapters into the EOSC Beyond ecosystem.

Overall, this deliverable documents the current status and implementation details of each adapter, along with associated repositories and technical details. The EOSC Integration Suite represents a critical step towards a more connected, federated, and interoperable open science infrastructure across Europe.

¹ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, EOSC Executive Board, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K. et al., *EOSC interoperability framework – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

1. Introduction

The EOSC Integration Suite (IS) in the EOSC Beyond project is designed to streamline the integration of tools, services, and research data across the EOSC ecosystem by offering modular, reusable adapters that adhere to the Interoperability Framework (IF) Guidelines. These adapters serve as middleware components, enabling interoperability by bridging diverse systems, protocols, and data formats. They are stored in a structured repository, managed through the IF Registry, Service Catalogue, and Marketplace, with discoverability and accessibility supported via the Resource Discovery Hub.

1.1. Scope and Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to provide a comprehensive overview of the initial set of adapters within the EOSC Beyond project. It aims to detail the development status, technical specifications, and integration strategies of these adapters, which facilitate seamless interaction between the EOSC Core, Horizontal, and Community services. It outlines their features, development status, and integration into the EOSC ecosystem, including timelines for release or implementation plans.

1.2. Structure of the document

The document is organised as follows:

- **Section 2:** Status of the Initial Set of Adapters: Details the development and implementation status of the adapters, divided into three subsections:
 - a. EOSC Core Service Adapters: Describes adapters for core services.
 - b. EOSC Horizontal Service Adapters: Covers adapters providing cross-domain functionality.
 - c. EOSC Community Service Adapters: Outlines the plan and development of adapters tailored for specific research communities.
- **Section 3:** Highlights the EOSC Integration Suite's role in enabling interoperability through adapters and outlines their development and integration.

2. Status of the Initial Set of Adapters

2.1. EOSC Core service adapters

EOSC Core Adapters are designed to integrate with and enhance the capabilities of the EOSC Core services. These services include Accounting for Services, Helpdesk, IF Registry, Messaging, Monitoring, PID, Research Product Accounting, Research Product Catalogue, and the Service Catalogue. This section outlines the current development status of each adapter, indicating whether it has been released and, if not, providing the expected release timeline.

2.1.1. Accounting for Services Adapter

Adapter Overview	
Description	<p>This initial version of the Accounting for Services Adapter focuses on the most commonly used functionalities to help Accounting clients interact with the Accounting service more efficiently. It provides a simplified interface for interacting with the REST API of the Accounting Service, significantly reducing development time and effort.</p> <p>The Accounting System serves as a platform for collecting, aggregating, and exchanging metrics across various infrastructures, providers, and projects. Its core functionality is exposed through a REST API, which this library is designed to interact with.</p> <p><i>Features</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrieve basic information such as IDs and names for projects, providers, and installations through simple function calls without handling low-level API requests. • Fetch existing metrics or submit new ones for specific installations using a straightforward interface that handles the details for you. • Access metrics grouped by project or provider to support higher-level reporting and analysis across infrastructures.
Organisation	National Infrastructures for Research and Technology (GRNET)
Linked Resource	Accounting for Services
Code Repository	https://github.com/ARGOeu/argo-acc-library
Documentation	https://github.com/ARGOeu/argo-acc-library/blob/main/README.md
Releases URL	https://github.com/ARGOeu/argo-acc-library/releases

Adapter Overview	
License	Apache License 2.0
Programming Language	Python
Version	0.1.0
Change Log	https://github.com/ARGOeu/argo-acc-library/blob/main/CHANGELOG.md
Status	Released

Table 1 - Accounting for Services Adapter

2.1.2. Helpdesk Adapter

Adapter Overview	
Description	<p>The Helpdesk Adapter enables seamless bidirectional synchronisation between two helpdesk platforms. It does this synchronisation as a standalone proxy that facilitates data flow without requiring direct integration with the platforms themselves. This approach is essential, as it provides flexibility and allows organisations to perform minimal development effort on their systems. Through its REST API, it enables real-time exchange of tickets, user data, and status updates, ensuring efficient and instant communication across platforms.</p> <p><i>Features</i></p> <p>The adapter simplifies the integration process and broadens its compatibility across various helpdesk technologies. Key enhancements include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Graphical Workflow Construction: Enables users to visually design integration workflows, simplifying configuration and customisation. ● Simplified Field Mapping and Configuration: Makes the mapping setup between helpdesk systems faster ● Modular Architecture: Allows easier extension and maintenance, enabling support for future integrations. ● Support for Multiple Helpdesk Technologies: The prerequisite for other helpdesk technologies is the support of the REST API.
Organisation	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
Linked Resource	EOSC Helpdesk
Code Repository	https://github.com/n8n-io/n8n

Adapter Overview	
Documentation	https://github.com/n8n-io/n8n/blob/master/README.md
Releases URL	https://github.com/n8n-io/n8n/releases
License	Sustainable Use License
Programming Language	Typescript
Version	1.110.1
Change Log	https://github.com/n8n-io/n8n/blob/master/CHANGELOG.md
Status	Released

Table 2 - Helpdesk Adapter

2.1.3. IF Registry Adapters

2.1.3.1. Interoperability Framework Guidelines Discovery Adapter

Adapter Overview	
Description	<p>The Interoperability Framework Guidelines Discovery adapter is an API wrapper offering easy search capabilities and access to the Interoperability Framework Registry Guidelines.</p> <p>It provides functionality for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Searching, browsing, and navigating the Interoperability Framework Guidelines, which are onboarded to an Interoperability Registry instance. • Ability to broker/route metadata information to service providers and any other EOSC Future Core component that uses such data.
Organisation	ATHENA Research Center (ARC)
Linked Resource	Interoperability Framework Registry
Code Repository	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/tree/main/clients/java/interoperability-registry-read
Documentation	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/blob/main/clients/java/interoperability-registry-read/README.md
Releases URL	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/releases
License	Apache License 2.0
Programming Language	Java
Version	1.0.0

Adapter Overview	
Change Log	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/blob/main/CHANGELOG.md
Status	Released

Table 3 - Interoperability Framework Guidelines Discovery Adapter

2.1.3.2. Interoperability Framework Guidelines Management Adapter

Adapter Overview	
Description	<p>The Interoperability Framework Guidelines Discovery adapter is an API wrapper offering capabilities for registering and managing guidelines.</p> <p>It provides functionality for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providers to register to the EOSC to become eligible for the onboarding of the Interoperability Framework Guidelines. • Providers to onboard their Guidelines into the EOSC Interoperability Registry. • Providers to view the list of Guidelines registered in the EOSC portal and perform a variety of actions, such as activate, deactivate, update to newer versions, and view statistics of Guidelines referenced by services.
Organisation	ATHENA Research Center (ARC)
Linked Resource	Interoperability Framework Registry
Code Repository	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/blob/main/clients/java/interoperability-registry-write/
Documentation	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/blob/main/clients/java/interoperability-registry-write/README.md
Releases URL	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/releases
License	Apache License 2.0
Programming Language	Java
Version	1.0.0
Change Log	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/blob/main/CHANGELOG.md
Status	Released

Table 4 - Interoperability Framework Guidelines Management Adapter

2.1.4. Messaging Adapter

Adapter Overview	
Description	<p>AMS currently provides a Python library offering essential services like message publishing, subscribing, and queue management. To address the growing and diverse needs of the project's services, the library will be enhanced with new features and improvements. The goal is to extend the capabilities of the AMS Python library by adding advanced message filtering, support for multiple message formats, and better error handling, ensuring greater flexibility and robustness.</p> <p><i>Features</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve and broaden existing functionalities to deliver a smoother and more comprehensive user experience. • Introduce new features, such as advanced filtering and enhanced error handling, to meet evolving client requirements. • Enable batch processing of messages and support for custom message formats based on defined schemas.
Organisation	National Infrastructures for Research and Technology (GRNET)
Linked Resource	ARGO Messaging Service
Code Repository	https://github.com/ARGOeu/argo-ams-library
Documentation	https://github.com/ARGOeu/argo-ams-library/blob/master/README.md
Releases URL	https://github.com/ARGOeu/argo-ams-library/releases
License	Apache License 2.0
Programming Language	Python
Version	1.0.0
Change Log	https://github.com/ARGOeu/argo-ams-library/blob/master/CHANGELOG.md
Status	Released

Table 5 - Messaging Adapter

2.1.5. Monitoring Adapter

Adapter Overview	
Description	Currently, the EOSC Monitoring Service is accessible only via a

Adapter Overview	
	<p>raw API, requiring each client to build custom integrations. The new Python Adapter wraps this API, simplifying integration by managing the underlying API calls. This enables developers to automate metric collection and exchange more efficiently.</p> <p><i>Features</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focuses on common API operations, such as publishing metrics, to reduce integration effort. • Abstracts complex API calls into easy-to-use Python functions with automatic handling of common parameters. • Converts raw API errors into meaningful exceptions and adds retry logic to improve reliability.
Organisation	National Infrastructures for Research and Technology (GRNET)
Linked Resource	EOSC Monitoring Service
Code Repository	https://github.com/ARGOeu/argo-mon-library
Documentation	https://github.com/ARGOeu/argo-mon-library/blob/main/README.md
Releases URL	https://github.com/ARGOeu/argo-mon-library/releases
License	Apache License 2.0
Programming Language	Python
Version	0.1.0
Change Log	https://github.com/ARGOeu/argo-mon-library/blob/main/CHANGELOG.md
Status	Released

Table 6 - Monitoring Adapter

2.1.6. PID Adapter

Adapter Overview	
Description	<p>A tool designed to streamline end-to-end communication between the PID (Persistent Identifier) service and EOSC Core components using standardised protocols and APIs. It builds on PyHandle, a Python client for the Handle System that enables the creation, retrieval, update, and deletion of persistent identifiers.</p> <p><i>Advantages</i></p>

Adapter Overview	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enable seamless communication between the PID service and EOSC Core components using standardised protocols and APIs. • Support reliable creation, updating, and resolution of persistent identifiers to enhance research output management. • Improve discoverability, accessibility, and reuse of research resources within the EOSC ecosystem. <p><i>Features</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mint, update, and delete PIDs • Search PIDs
Organisation	National Infrastructures for Research and Technology (GRNET), Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen (GWDG)
Linked Resource	PID Service
Code Repository	https://github.com/EUDAT-B2HANDLE/pyhandle
Documentation	https://github.com/EUDAT-B2HANDLE/PYHANDLE/blob/master/README.md
Releases URL	https://github.com/EUDAT-B2HANDLE/PYHANDLE/releases https://pypi.org/project/pyhandle/
License	Apache License 2.0
Programming Language	Python
Version	1.5.0
Change Log	N/A
Status	Released

Table 7 - PID Adapter

2.1.7. Research Product Accounting Adapters

2.1.7.1. COUNTER Adapter for DSpace platform

Adapter Overview	
Description	The Adapter connects DSpace 7 and 8 platforms with the EOSC Accounting for Research Products (OpenAIRE UsageCounts). The adapter is available as patches for the DSpace versions, and pull requests have been issued to the DSpace codebase, which must be reviewed, accepted, and merged by the DSpace community.
Organisation	OpenAIRE AMKE

Adapter Overview	
Linked Resource	EOSC IF Interoperability Guidelines for Research Products Accounting
Code Repository	Repository with patches for DSpace: https://github.com/openaire/OpenAIRE-Piwik-DSpace Pull Request for the integration in the DSpace codebase: https://github.com/openaire/DSpace/pull/2/files
Documentation	https://openaire.github.io/usage-statistics-guidelines
Releases URL	https://github.com/openaire/OpenAIRE-Piwik-DSpace/releases
License	BSD-3-Clause license
Programming Language	Java
Version	1.0.0
Change Log	N/A (First release)
Status	Released

Table 8 - COUNTER Adapter for DSpace platform

2.1.7.2. COUNTER Adapter for ePrints platform

Adapter Overview	
Description	The Adapter connects ePrints platforms with the EOSC Accounting for Research Products (OpenAIRE UsageCounts).
Organisation	OpenAIRE AMKE
Linked Resource	EOSC IF Interoperability Guidelines for Research Products Accounting
Code Repository	https://github.com/openaire/EPrints-OAPiwik
Documentation	https://openaire.github.io/usage-statistics-guidelines
Releases URL	https://github.com/openaire/EPrints-OAPiwik/releases
License	CC0-1.0
Programming Language	Perl
Version	1.0
Change Log	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> v1.0 Dimitris Pierrakos dpierrakos@gmail.com, Karlo Hrenovic karlo.hrenovic@irb.hr, Alen Vodopijevic alen@irb.hr Initial version based on "PIRUS/IRUS-UK PUSH Implementation" http://files.eprints.org/971
Status	Released

Table 9 - COUNTER Adapter for ePrints platform

2.1.7.3. Generic Usage Activity Tracker for OpenAIRE

Adapter Overview	
Description	The Adapter connects generic repository platforms with the EOSC Accounting for Research Products (OpenAIRE UsageCounts).
Organisation	OpenAIRE AMKE
Linked Resource	EOSC IF Interoperability Guidelines for Research Products Accounting
Code Repository	https://github.com/openaire/Generic-Matomo-Tracker
Documentation	https://openaire.github.io/usage-statistics-guidelines/
Releases URL	https://github.com/openaire/Generic-Matomo-Tracker/releases
License	CC0
Programming Language	Python
Version	1.0.1
Change Log	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • change comment on required python version • added license file
Status	Released

Table 10 - Generic Usage Activity Tracker for OpenAIRE

2.1.8. Research Product Catalogue Adapter (OAI-PMH end-point for SQL Postgres Database)

Adapter Overview	
Description	This Adapter consists of a Spring Boot application designed to facilitate the export of metadata records in compliance with the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). The application operates as an OAI-PMH endpoint that efficiently collects and exports metadata directly from a PostgreSQL database. By adhering to OAI-PMH standards, this application enhances the accessibility and interoperability of metadata across diverse digital libraries and repositories.
Organisation	OpenAIRE AMKE
Linked Resource	EOSC-IF Interoperability Guidelines for Data Sources to onboard Research Products

Adapter Overview	
Code Repository	https://github.com/micheleartini/dnet-oai-server
Documentation	https://zenodo.org/records/13938870
Releases URL	https://github.com/micheleartini/dnet-oai-server/releases
License	AGPL-3.0
Programming Language	Java
Version	1.0.0
Change Log	N/A - First release
Status	Released

Table 11 - Research Product Catalogue Adapter (OAI-PMH end-point for SQL Postgres Database)

2.1.9. Service Catalogue Adapters

2.1.9.1. Service Discovery Adapter

Adapter Overview	
Description	<p>This adapter provides searching and listing functionality for the onboarded resources in the Service Catalogue.</p> <p>It provides functionality for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Searching, browsing, and navigating the Services and Providers that are onboarded to a Service Catalogue instance. • Ability to broker/route metadata information to service providers and any other EOSC Core component that uses such data.
Organisation	ATHENA Research Center (ARC)
Linked Resource	Service Catalogue
Code Repository	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/tree/main/clients/java/service-registry-read
Documentation	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/tree/main/clients/java/service-registry-read/README.md
Releases URL	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/releases
License	Apache License 2.0
Programming Language	Java
Version	1.0.0
Change Log	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/blob/main/CHANGELOG.md
Status	Released

Table 12 - Service Discovery Adapter

2.1.9.2. Provider and Service Management Adapter

Adapter Overview	
Description	<p>This adapter will allow providers to easily onboard and manage their resources in the Service Catalogue.</p> <p>It provides functionality for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providers to register to the EOSC to become eligible for the onboarding of resources. • Providers to onboard their services into the EOSC Service Catalogue. • Providers to view the list of services registered in the

Adapter Overview	
	EOSC portal and perform a variety of actions, such as activate, deactivate, and view usage statistics.
Organisation	ATHENA Research Center (ARC)
Linked Resource	Service Catalogue
Code Repository	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/tree/main/clients/java/service-registry-write
Documentation	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/tree/main/clients/java/service-registry-write/README.md
Releases URL	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/releases
License	Apache License 2.0
Programming Language	Java
Version	1.0.0
Change Log	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/blob/main/CHANGELOG.md
Status	Released

Table 13 - Provider and Service Management Adapter

2.1.9.3. Administration and Audit Adapter

Adapter Overview	
Description	<p>This adapter will offer administration and auditing of providers, services, and catalogues. It provides functionality for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Managing the onboarding process (approve or reject an application). • Managing the catalogue of providers and services, and auditing the validity of the catalogue entries. • Interacting with providers through established EOSC channels (Helpdesk). • Adding regional or thematic catalogues.
Organisation	ATHENA Research Center (ARC)
Linked Resource	Service Catalogue
Code Repository	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/tree/main/clients/java/service-registry-admin
Documentation	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/tree/main/clients/java/service-registry-admin/README.md

Adapter Overview	
Releases URL	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/releases
License	Apache License 2.0
Programming Language	Java
Version	API 5.1.1 - Generator 7.14.0
Change Log	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/blob/main/CHANGELOG.md
Status	Released

Table 14 - Administration and Audit Adapter

2.1.9.4. Insights and Statistics Adapter

Adapter Overview	
Description	This adapter will help providers get access to statistics and insights for onboarded resources. It provides functionality for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Catalogue statistics. • Recommendations and insights based on the catalogue feedback and content.
Organisation	ATHENA Research Center (ARC)
Linked Resource	Service Catalogue
Code Repository	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/tree/main/clients/java/service-registry-stats
Documentation	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/tree/main/clients/java/service-registry-stats/README.md
Releases URL	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/releases
License	Apache License 2.0
Programming Language	Java
Version	1.0.0
Change Log	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/horizontal-adapters/blob/main/CHANGELOG.md
Status	Released

Table 15 - Insights and Statistics Adapter

2.2. EOOSC Horizontal service adapters

EOOSC Horizontal Adapters provide generic, cross-domain functionality to support integration across a wide range of scientific disciplines. They include components such as the EOOSC Data

Transfer Client, JupyterLab libraries for service provisioning and data staging, tools for metadata extraction from TOSCA templates, mechanisms for accessing data across heterogeneous hosting environments, and Python libraries for managing the EOSC Exchange Jupyter services.

2.2.1. EOSC Data Transfer Client

Adapter Overview	
Description	Data Transfer is a horizontal EOSC service, consisting of an API and a GUI, which is integrated with the EOSC Marketplace. Although the main client of this service is the EOSC Marketplace, its API can also be used directly by other EOSC services (e.g., the Deployment Service) and researchers. To facilitate this direct usage, adapters shall be developed for the Data Transfer API. Python client for interacting with the EOSC Data Transfer API .
Organisation	European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN)
Linked Resource	EOSC Data Transfer
Code Repository	https://gitlab.cern.ch/batistal/eosc-data-transfer-client
Documentation	https://eosc-data-transfer-client.docs.cern.ch
Releases URL	https://gitlab.cern.ch/batistal/eosc-data-transfer-client/-/releases
License	Apache 2.0
Programming Language	Python
Version	Jun 19, 2025
Change Log	First version
Status	Released

Table 16 - EOSC Data Transfer Client

2.2.2. JupyterLab libraries for service provisioning and data staging

Adapter Overview	
Description	This adapter is responsible for providing extensions in Jupyter that allow users to employ the functionality of the DS from a Jupyter Notebook. <i>Features</i>

Adapter Overview	
	<p>The goal is to facilitate the creation of reproducible experiments, which include in the narrative of the experiment:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The provisioning of the virtualized computing infrastructure required to reproduce the experiment as a TOSCA template deployable through the DS. 2. The staging of dataset(s) into storage allocated in step (1), from any supported open data repository, such as Zenodo or B2SHARE, or even from relevant data spaces.
Organisation	Valencia Polytechnic University (UPV)
Linked Resource	Deployment Service
Code Repository	https://github.com/grycap/apricotlab
Documentation	https://github.com/grycap/apricotlab/blob/main/README.md
Releases URL	https://github.com/grycap/apricotlab/releases
License	BSD 3-Clause License
Programming Language	TypeScript and Python
Version	1.0.0
Change Log	First version
Status	Released

Table 17 - JupyterLab libraries for service provisioning and data staging

2.2.3. Metadata gathering of TOSCA templates

Adapter Overview	
Description	This adapter facilitates access to the TOSCA template metadata offered by the DS through its OAI-PMH interface. These can be a curated set of TOSCA templates that are commonly used by the users of an EOSC Node. This will facilitate automated resource discovery and integration with third-party services in the EOSC Exchange that require the functionality of deploying virtualised infrastructure.
Organisation	Valencia Polytechnic University (UPV)
Linked Resource	Deployment Service
Code Repository	https://github.com/grycap/im-oaipmh-client
Documentation	https://github.com/grycap/im-oaipmh-client/blob/main/README.md

Adapter Overview	
Releases URL	https://github.com/grycap/im-oaipmh-client/releases
License	GPL-3.0
Programming Language	Python
Version	1.0.0
Change Log	First version
Status	Released

Table 18 - Metadata gathering of TOSCA templates

2.2.4. Data access across hosting environments

Adapter Overview	
Description	The data access adapter within the JupyterLab environment enables seamless integration with external storage services, allowing users to access these resources as if they were local to the Jupyter server.
Organisation	Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH (FZJ)
Linked Resource	Deployment Service, Extension
Code Repository	https://github.com/jsc-jupyter/jupyterlab-data-mount/
Documentation	https://jsc-jupyter.github.io/jupyterlab-data-mount/
Releases URL	https://github.com/jsc-jupyter/jupyterlab-data-mount/releases https://pypi.org/project/jupyterlab-data-mount/
License	BSD-3-Clause license
Programming Language	Python, Typescript
Version	1.0.0
Change Log	CHANGELOG
Status	Released

Table 19 - Data access across hosting environments

2.2.5. Python libraries for the EOSC exchange Jupyter service management

Adapter Overview	
Description	This adapter is responsible for providing a way to control and manage JupyterHub and Jupyter server via a fedcloud Python

Adapter Overview	
	client. The goal is to allow users to remotely use JupyterHub deployments as computational units, which they can effectively control and use tools like Papermill to use the full potential of the JupyterHub platform.
Organisation	Institute of Informatics, Slovak Academy of Sciences (IISAS)
Linked Resource	Deployment Service
Code Repository	https://github.com/tdviet/fedcloudclient
Documentation	https://fedcloudclient.fedcloud.eu
Releases URL	https://github.com/tdviet/fedcloudclient/releases
License	MIT
Programming Language	Python
Version	v1.4.4-beyond
Change Log	CHANGELOG
Status	Released

Table 20 - Python libraries for the EOSC exchange Jupyter service management

2.3. EOSC Community service adapters

EOSC Community adapters are libraries that research communities use extensively to access and consume services or research products from the EOSC Resource Discovery Hub. They will be approved and onboarded by the Pilot Nodes to facilitate access to their services onboarded to the EOSC Beyond Federated Catalogue. If no suitable adapter is identified, the Pilot Nodes will design potential adapters to improve the accessibility and usability of their services for other research communities within the EOSC. This effort is coordinated by ACC Cyfronet, with active contributions from Pilot Nodes representing participating organisations, which currently are EGI Pilot Node, Instruct-ERIC, LifeWatch, NI4OS, e-INFRA CZ, NFDI, METROFOOD-RI, CESSDA, CNB-CSIC, and ENES.

2.3.1. Implementation Plan for the EOSC Community Adapters

To ensure effective discovery, integration, and access to Community Adapters within the EOSC Beyond ecosystem, a structured plan has been established. This plan outlines a phased approach involving recognition, documentation, and onboarding activities, carried out in collaboration with the Pilot Nodes and coordinated efforts across the network.

1. The first step, which has already been completed, involved the identification and recognition of the Exchange services that the Pilot Nodes plan to contribute to the

Network of Pilot Nodes. These services form the foundation upon which Community Adapters will be built or integrated.

2. The second step, currently in progress, focuses on collecting and organising detailed information regarding the availability and readiness of adapters that correspond to the Exchange services provided by the Pilot Nodes.
3. The final step, which is planned for the upcoming phases, will involve the onboarding of validated Community Adapters into the EOOSC Beyond Integration Suite. This will ensure that the adapters are fully accessible, discoverable, and reusable by other communities within EOOSC, thereby facilitating broader adoption and interoperability across the federated ecosystem.

2.3.2. Exchange Services as Foundations for Adapter Development

The table below lists the service types and corresponding service names of the Exchange services that the Pilot Nodes intend to contribute to the Network of Pilot Nodes.

Service Type	Service Name
Data Repositories and Discovery Services (Data Sources)	Research Data Repositories
Data Repositories and Discovery Services (Data Sources)	Thematic Repositories
Data Repositories and Discovery Services (Data Sources)	Institutional Repositories
Data Repositories and Discovery Services (Data Sources)	Data Aggregators
Data Repositories and Discovery Services (Data Sources)	Data Archives
Compute Resources	High-Performance Computing (HPC) Resources
Compute Resources	Cloud Computing Services
Data Storage Solutions	Cloud Storage Solutions

Data Storage Solutions	File Storage in Computing Infrastructures
Data Storage Solutions	Block Storage Services
Networking Services	Data Transfer
Data Processing and Analysis Services and APIs	Metadata Services
Data Processing and Analysis Services and APIs	Data Processing Services
Data Processing and Analysis Services and APIs	Data Visualisation Services
Data Processing and Analysis Services and APIs	Virtual Computing Environments
Data Processing and Analysis Services and APIs	Other programmatic services
Community and Support Resources	Training and Tutorials
Data Management Planning Services	Data Management Planning Services
Monitoring and Data Quality Assurance Services	Monitoring and Data Quality Assurance Services
Data Collection Services	Data Collection Services
Data Collection Services	Core service technologies or services supporting federating capabilities

Table 21 - Identified Exchange Services and their classification

3. Conclusion

The EOSC Integration Suite, as outlined in the EOSC Beyond project, is pivotal in fostering interoperability within the European Open Science Cloud ecosystem by providing an initial set of adapters for Core, Horizontal, and Community Services. These adapters bridge diverse systems and data formats, adhering to the EOSC Interoperability Framework Guidelines, and are managed through the IF Registry, Service Catalogue, and Resource Discovery Hub. This deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the adapters' development progress, technical details, implementation timelines for the Core and Horizontal adapters, as well as presents the implementation plan specific to the Community adapters. It highlights the critical role these adapters play in enabling fluid, scalable connections across diverse EOSC services.

Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
AMoS	ARGO Monitoring Service
AMS	ARGO Messaging Service
BSD	Berkeley Software Distribution
CC0	Creative Commons Zero (Public Domain Dedication)
DS	Deployment Service
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GPL	General Public License
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HPC	High-Performance Computing
IF	Interoperability Framework
IS	Integration Suite
JupyterHub	Multi-user server for Jupyter notebooks
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology (license)
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
Papermill	Tool for parameterising and executing Jupyter Notebooks
PID	Persistent Identifier
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
SQL	Structured Query Language
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications